

Proportional Assessment of Oral Tablets Having Complex of Cyclodextrin And BCS Class II Drugs

Avinash Gupta^{1*}, Vijay Sharma², Ashutosh Sharma³, Manish K. Gupta⁴, Praveen Jaiswal⁵

¹*Poddar International College of Pharmacy, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India*

²*Goenka College of Pharmacy, Lachhmangarh, Sikar, Rajasthan, India*

³*Jaipur College of Pharmacy, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India*

⁴*School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Jaipur National University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India*

⁵*Lords University, Alwar, Rajasthan, India*

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Corresponding author: Avinash Gupta

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Abstract

Today in Pharma area it turns into an extreme work to make a formula of active molecules having poor water dissolvability. This explanation, that at present different beneficial active molecules don't go to the market because of less disintegration and at last less bioavailability. According to the BCS classifications drugs like Elvitegravir which has a place with class II have the less solvency and great penetrability. In this way, it turns into a basic test for a formulator, to figure these medications having the whimsical or non-uniform medication discharge profile, drug retention influenced by the food, and from one patient to another and non-uniform bioavailability all through the GIT. In the Pharmaceutical business, Complexation of poor watery dissolvable API with the Cyclodextrin is most alluring strategy for upgrading the medication dissolution. This procedure of medication complexation is likewise promptly acknowledged by the various administrative specialists. Cyclodextrins can oblige different lipophilic medications in its hydrophobic focal hole. These are torus molded design having external hydrophilic surface. These mixtures make the buildings with the lipophilic medications without change in their lipophilic property and their pharmacological properties. In the current investigation solubilization and delivery properties of Elvitegravir was attempted to upgrade by complexation with the β CD and HP β CD. Extend of drug complexation was analyzed through phase solubility method. End results were manufactured using the drug cyclodextrin complex and investigate for its physicochemical properties.

Keywords: Complexation, Cyclodextrin, Water solubility, Bioavailability, Drug Release

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Introduction

For enhancement of solubility of poorly water soluble drug various techniques were used. Out of them complexation of drug with the cyclodextrins is most efficient. Zhang et al. (2015), deliberate a complex of the API with the cyclodextrins. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the API i.e. oridonin. Techniques utilized for scheme the formula was evaporating the solvent. Shah et al. (2015) deliberate a complex of the API with the cyclodextrins. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the API i.e. Paclitaxal. Techniques utilized for scheme the formula was evaporating the solvent. Drug gets entrapped in the molecules of the complexing agent. Shaikh et al. (2011) deliberate a complex of the API with the cyclodextrins. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the API i.e. Candesartan. Techniques utilized for scheme the formula was evaporating the solvent. Yavuz et al. (2010) deliberate a complex of the API with the cyclodextrins. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the API i.e. Exemestane. Techniques utilized for scheme the formula was kneading and colyophilization. Chowdary et al. (2012) deliberate solid oral dose of the API. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the three different antiviral APIs. Maheshwari et al. (2011) deliberate solid oral dose of the API. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the API i.e. Furosemide. Techniques utilized for scheme the formula was hydrotrophy. Talukder et al. (2011)

deliberate dispersions of the API. The intention of this experiment was to convalesce the Solublization and biological availability of the APIs i.e. ibuprofen, carbamazepine, and nifedipine. Techniques utilized for scheme the formula was co-grinding. HPC was used as APIs carrier with or without solvent. Other formulations are like Complex of caffeine and Benzocaine (Higuchi WI. *et al*; 1965), Complex of hydroquinone and digitoxin (Higuchi T. *et al*; 1974), Complex of caffeine and ergot alkaloids (Zoglio MA. *et al*; 1969), Povidone (Chowdary KPR. *et al*; 2006). β -cyclodextrin complex of Etoricoxib (Santosh K.R. *et al*; 2009). β and HP β -cyclodextrin complex of Celecoxib (Chowdary KPR. *et al*; 2008).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Elvitegravir was received as gift sample from M/s Eli Lilly and Company India, β – Cyclodextrin, HP β –Cyclodextrin. Talcum and Compritol from M/s Arihant Pharma, Gum Arabic from M/s Loba Chemie, Polyplasdone XL 10 from M/s Natco Pharma and SMC from M/s JRS Pharma

Solubility Estimation

This process performed according the existing reference (Higuchi T. *et al*; 1965). In the 0.1 litre Volumetric glass container 200 mg of Elvitegravir was added with 20 ml of each solution. These solutions were placed on the manual type of shaker and operated for overnight at the normal environmental conditions. Next day, 5 ml aliquots taken and after filtration and dilution with N/10 HCl, these are scanned in spectrophotometer at the λ of 313 nm.

Manufacturing of Elvitegravir Tablets

Procedure

All components are weighed accurately, as per the composition of table 3.10 and labeled properly. Drug Elvitegravir, SMC and PPL XL-10 were added together in a SS container and passed thru mesh no. 20. According to the formulation β CD or HP β CD taken and mixed with powder blend. Granulating solution Prepared by addition and mixing Gum Arabic in the de ionized water. Stir the solution properly to completely dissolve the granulating agent. Then granulating solution transferred to the powder mix of API uniformly and mixed. This wetted mixture dried at 60°C for 35 min to acquire the semidried mixture. This mixture passed thru mess 12 to acquire the desired granular size. If require these granules were further dried to attain the wanted moisture content. These semi dried granules further dried for 1 hr. and passed thru mess 20. Thereafter, these granules were added with lubricants properly to accomplish the uniform final blend.

Physicochemical Parameters of Tablets

Assay

Collect the 10 units of dosage form and crushed in the pastle mortar. Sample qty. of powder similar to the dose of drug taken. This sample quantity was treated with methyl alcohol several times to dissolve out the Elvitegravir in methanol. This solution was filtered with whatmann filter paper. This drug solution was further diluted with the dissolution media of N/10 HCl. The qty. of Elvitegravir in the solution was calculated using spectroscopy at λ of 313 nm. Standard curve was utilized for the quantification of Elvitegravir in the solution.

Tablet Strength

Strength of unit dosage form was measured by Dr. Sheluinger tablet strength analyzer.

Friability

Fragility of unit dosage form was measured by the apparatus of M/s Elecrolab India.

Disintegration Time

Erosion or de-aggregation in the unit dosage form was measured by DT apparatus of M/s Elecrolab India.

Drug Release

Drug release of Elvitegravir was studied in Elecrolab Dissolution Equipment. For the dissolution following parameters were kept

Apparatus: USP Type II (Paddle)

Media: N/10 hydrochloric acid

Volume: 0.9 Litre RPM: 50

Temperature of Media: 37°C $\pm$ 1°C

Sample Volume: 5 ml

One unit of dosage form was dropped in the each basket of Dissolution Equipment. At the defined time interval sample quantity taken and treated with the dissolution media. After proper dilution and treatment the sample was run in the spectroscopy at the λ of 313 nm. Quantification of drug amount in the sample was carried using standard curve. The test was proceeded in triplicate (n=3).

Table 1: Manufacturing Formula Prepared with Cyclodextrins

Composition					
Component	E 1 (Qty/ tab.)	E 2 (Qty/ tab.)	E 3 (Qty/ tab.)	E 4 (Qty /tab.)	E 5 (Qty/ tab.)
Elvitegravir	100.00 mg	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
βCD	0.00	100.00 mg	200.00 mg	0.00	0.00
HPβCD	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00 mg	200.00 mg
Gum Arabic	5.00 mg				
PPL XL-10	20.00 mg				
Talcum	2.00 mg				
Compritol	3.00 mg				
SMC up to	550.00 mg				

RESULTS

Effect of Drug Complex on Solubility

Table 2: Effect of β-Cyclodextrin quantity on Solubilization of Elvitegravir

Concⁿ of β CD	Concⁿ of Elvitegravir
0 mM	2.13 mM
1 mM	4.22 mM
2 mM	3.93 mM
3 mM	4.95 mM
6 mM	6.64 mM

Table 3: Effect of HP β-Cyclodextrin quantity on Solubilization of Elvitegravir

Concⁿ of HPβ CD	Concⁿ of Elvitegravir
0 mM	2.13 mM
1 mM	3.11 mM
2 mM	3.06 mM

3 mM	4.08 mM
6 mM	5.06 mM

Fig. 1.0: Impact of Cyclodextrin on the Solubility of Elvitegravir

Drug Complexation was manufactured using multiple quantity of β CD and HP β CD. These complexes were studied for water solubility study. As the quantity of Cyclodextrins increases solubilization of Elvitegravir get increases.

Evaluation of Tablets

Table 4: Physical Parameters of Tab. Manufactured with Cyclodextrins

Composition	Assay	Tablet Strength	Friability	DT
E 1	100.51 mg	5 – 6 Kp	0.48 %	3.9 min
E 2	99.95 mg	4 – 5.5 Kp	0.65 %	2.15 min
E 3	99.68 mg	4 – 6.0 Kp	0.23 %	2.43 min
E 4	100.05 mg	4.5 – 6.0 Kp	0.41 %	15.1 min
E 5	99.45 mg	4 – 5.5 Kp	0.81 %	20.1 min

Table 5: Drug Release of Tab. Manufactured with Cyclodextrins

Time	% Release ($X \pm SD$)				
	E 1	E 2	E 3	E 4	E 5
5 min	21.23 % $\pm$ 1.18	77.95 % $\pm$ 1.95	82.43 % $\pm$ 1.43	19.18 % $\pm$ 1.25	12.09 % $\pm$ 1.53
10 min	35.05 % $\pm$ 1.45	88.41 % $\pm$ 1.45	97.18 % $\pm$ 1.92	46.28 % $\pm$ 1.43	18.82 % $\pm$ 1.72

20 min	44.71 % ± 1.41	91.55 % ± 1.56	99.55 % ± 1.55	76.38 % ± 1.75	33.45 % ± 1.93
30 min	51.81 % ± 1.95	99.45 % ± 1.48	100.0 % ± 0.95	82.65 % ± 1.76	50.72 % ± 1.45

Fig. 2: Release of Tab. prepared using Cyclodextrins

Fig. 3: Logarithmic Release of Tab. Manufactured with Cyclodextrins

Table 6: Values of (r) according to Zero order and First order Kinetics

Composition	r value	
	Zero order kinetics	Zero order kinetics
E 1	0.917	0.953
E 2	0.862	0.905

E 3	0.592	0.983
E 4	0.885	0.957
E 5	0.981	0.997

As per the observed results physical parameters of the unit dosage form were satisfactory and as accord to Pharmacopoeial requirement. All Compositions qualify the DT test as per pharmacopoeia limit of NMT 15 min

As per the observed values of (r) according to Zero order and First order Kinetics the release of Elvitegravir looking to be best fitted in first order because of their higher values.

The different data of release suggest, fast and higher release can be achieved after complexation of Elvitegravir with the β CD as compared to drug release with the HP β CD. Among all the ratio of Elvitegravir and β CD (1:2) provide greater release in instance to any other dosage unit.

Conclusion

From the observed results following conclusions are made.

- Release behavior of Elvitegravir is majorly determined by the complexing agent.
- Complexation of Elvitegravir with the β CD gives higher release contrary to the release from plain drug or Drug HP β CD complex.
- Drug β CD complex (1:2) increases the release to 15.35 fold contrary to the release from plain drug.

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